

Study of the Effectiveness of Extracts of Black Pepper Fruits (*Piper nigrum*) on the Growth of Fungi Isolated from Some Food Products

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Abstract

The research was carried out to estimate the biological effectiveness of water and alcoholic extracts from black pepper fruits on the growth of some fungi isolated from food products (rice seeds, nuts, noodles, and spaghetti). Various fungi linked with these products were isolated, including *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus terreus*, *Penicillium* spp, *Alternaria* spp, *Curvularia* spp, *Rhizoctonia* spp, and *Drechslera* spp. The results displayed that the type of extract meaningfully affected the levels of fungal contamination. The alcoholic extract was more effective in reducing contamination rates with a rate of 27.2%, while the rates were 38.75% and 34.0% for the cold and hot water extracts, respectively. The concentration of the extract also played a crucial role in reducing contamination rates, with a 70% concentration being the most effective, resulting in a contamination rate of 5%, while a 50% concentration was the second most effective with a contamination rate of 12.6%. The contamination rate increased to 90% in control group. Furthermore, the outcomes showed that sensitivity of the fungi varied according to the type of extract, with the alcoholic extract being more efficient in diminishing fungal contamination contrasted to water extracts (cold and hot). Among the *Aspergillus niger* was the most affected, with contamination rates of (25, 31.25, 22.5) % for the cold water, hot water, and alcoholic extracts respectively.

Introduction

Medicinal plants and their seeds were known about 6,000 years ago, since the dawn of civilizations, when large quantities of plants used in ancient medicine were found among the Pharaohs. The demand for medicinal plants has increased and aromatics globally and locally because of their great economic importance because of using them in many fields, including the pharmaceutical industry. industries of Food, cosmetic and chemical, so the demand for these plants has increased, especially in industrialized countries Developed because it is a non-traditional crop and has many uses, in addition to its participation in improving agricultural exports Manufactured and raw [1,2]. It is known that certain fungi have the ability to produce mycotoxins, which are

metabolic products of some fungi, including *Fusarium* spp., *Penicillium* spp., and *Aspergillus* spp. These fungi grow on various grains, nuts, and fats, thereby influencing both native production and the universal economy [3]. Mycotoxins are commonly found in crops harvested and stored with high moisture content, where the safe storage moisture limits to prevent fungal growth are not adhered to. Several factors influence the production of mycotoxins, including the type of fungus, the type of food, and the influence of heat and moisture, as well as the levels of oxygen and carbon dioxide [4]. various foodstuffs can become polluted with fungi and toxins due to unsuitable stowage before, after, and during collection. The extent of pollution is influenced by several causes, including

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pH, moisture, the physical characteristics of the seeds, and contact to insects or microbes. Fungi are also known for secreting enzymes that impact much of the food content. Mycotoxins, which are typically associated with human and animal food, arise from fungal contamination, referred to as direct contamination. This contamination can promote fungal growth during various stages of production, transportation, or storage. Wheat, rice, legumes, and nuts are commonly consumed foods, and poor storage is one of the parts that leads to increased evolution, especially fungi, which secrete toxins in foods, leading to their destruction. These toxins affect human health, causing many diseases. [5-7].

Research has shown that plants have a physiological and medicinal effect, as they have been used to treat many diseases, and that they have the ability to kill and inhibit many pathogenic microorganisms, and their side effects are less compared to various industrial drugs, as they are safe to use [8]. Black pepper (*Piper nigrum*) is a widely consumed medicinal plant belonging to the Piperaceae family [9]. This plant contains several important chemical components, including resins, sugars (Saccharides, Gemic Substances), amino acids, terpenoid compounds [10,11], and other minerals. The plant has been used to combat certain pathogens, either as a water or alcoholic extract or as a powder for seed treatment or storage. For instance, black pepper has been used to treat rice seeds to inhibit the growth of *A. sydowii* [12]. Due to the limited studies on the effectiveness of extracts in reducing or combating pathogens, this study was guided with the following objectives:

1. Isolation and identify some fungi growing on many grain and food products.
2. To study the influence of water and alcoholic extracts from black pepper fruits (*Piper nigrum*) in inhibition the growth of fungi isolated from grain and food products in the laboratory.

Materials and Methods

Collecting samples and estimating the percentage of grains from different market including (30) samples (rice, nuts, noodles, and spaghetti) offered for sale in the local markets from different areas of Najaf Al-Ashraf, Kufa, Abu Sakhir, and Abbasiya, twice every ten days. Samples in each replicate were sorted to calculate the percentage.

1. Culture Media

A. Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA): Prepared according to [3] by taking 200 grams of potato extract, washing and cutting it into small pieces, placing it in a metal container, adding one liter of distilled water, and boiling for 20 minutes. The mixture was then filtered through clean cheesecloth, and 20 gm of dextrose and 15 grams of agar were added. The solution was sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 20 minutes at

1atmosphere pressure. This medium was used for isolating and identifying the studied fungi.

B. Potato Dextrose Broth: Prepared using the same method as (A) but without adding agar to the filtrate. This medium was used to propagate fungal cultures [13].

2. Isolation and Identification of Fungi from Food Products (rice, nuts, noodles, and spaghetti)

The food products were surface-sterilized with a 2% sodium hypochlorite solution for 3 minutes, then rinsed with sterile water, dried, and plated on PDA plates with 40 mg/l chloramphenicol to inhibit bacterial growth. Five pieces of each food item were placed in each plate, four at the edges and one in the center. The plates were incubated at 25°C ± 2°C for 7 days [14]. After incubation, the fungal isolates were purified by transferring a disc from each colony to a new PDA plate, and this step was repeated several times.

Fungal isolates of *Aspergillus* were identified based on the taxonomic characteristics described by [15]. *Penicillium* spp. isolates were identified based on [16], and isolates of *Drechslera*, *Curvularia*, *Alternaria*, and *Rhizoctonia* were identified based on [17,18,22].

3.Preparation of Black Pepper Fruit Extracts

Samples of Black Pepper Fruit were collected from local markets and were cleaned, dried, and ground in a laboratory mill for use in preparing extracts.

A. Preparation of Black Pepper Fruit Extracts:

A. Water Extract:

The method described by [19] based on [20] was followed. 10 gm of dried plant powder were placed in a 500 ml glass flask with 200 ml distilled water. The plant material was mixed using a magnetic stirrer for 15 minutes and then left to settle for an hour. The mixture was filtered through three layers of gauze to remove large particles and then centrifuged for 15 minutes to separate smaller particles, resulting in a clear solution. A stock solution was obtained and used to prepare concentrations of 30%, 50%, and 70% by adding 30 ml of the stock solution and adjusting the volume to 100 ml with distilled water. The same method was used for preparing other concentrations.

B. hot water extract:

For the hot water extract, the same procedure was followed, (3. A.) but boiled distilled water at 100°C was used.

C. Organic Solvent (Alcohol) Extract:

The alcoholic extract was prepared using the Soxhlet extraction method as described by [21] and [23]. 10 gm of dried plant powder were extracted sequentially using 200 ml of ethyl alcohol for 24 hours. The extract was then concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 40-45°C to determine the biological activity. To prepare the required concentrations, 1 gm of the dried extract was dissolved in 3 ml of the same solvent (ethyl alcohol) and diluted to 100 ml to obtain a 1% stock solution.

From this, concentrations of (30, 50, 70) % were prepared.

4. Testing the Efficacy of Black Pepper Fruit Extracts (Cold, Hot, and Alcoholic) on the Inhibition of Fungal Growth Isolated from Food Products

In this experiment, water extracts (cold and hot) and alcoholic extracts of black pepper fruit were tested for their ability to inhibit the growth of fungi isolated from food products. Three concentrations of each extract (30, 50, 70) % were prepared and mixed with the sterilized Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium. After cooling, 0.5 cm discs of each fungal colony were placed at the center of the plates [24]. The plates were incubated at 25°C for 7 days with four replicates per treatment and a control for each fungus. Once the fungal colonies reached the edge of the plates, the radial growth inhibition rate was calculated by measuring two perpendicular diameters and applying the inhibition formula according to [25] in [26]

$$\text{Inhibition percentage (\%)} = \frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_1} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where:

R₁ is the maximum radial growth of the fungal colony in the control plates.

R₂ is the maximum radial growth of the fungal colony in the plates containing the extract.

5. Statistical Analysis

All experimental results were analyzed using the Completely Randomized Design (C.R.D) model. Means

were compared using the Least Significant Difference (L.S.D) test at a significance level of 0.05 [12].

Results and Discussion

1. Fungi Isolated from Food

Various fungi were isolated from rice seeds, including *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *A. terreus*, *Penicillium* spp., *Curvularia* spp, *Rhizoctonia* spp, and *Drechslera* spp. Additionally, several fungi were isolated from nuts, including *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. terreus*, *Alternaria* spp, *Penicillium* spp, and *Curvularia*.

On the other hand, several fungi were isolated from noodles and spaghetti such as *A. fumigatus*, *A. flavus*, *Drechslera* spp, *Rhizoctonia* spp, and *Curvularia* spp were identified. The fungi selected for further study included *A. flavus*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. niger*, *A. terreus*, *Penicillium* spp, *Drechslera* spp, *Rhizoctonia* spp, *Alternaria* spp, and *Curvularia* spp due to their high frequency on the studied food products. Figure (1)

The moisture content of grains greatly controls the safety of their storage, as the moisture content of grains is one of the features associated to the weight of the dry matter, as their infection in storage is caused by some of fungi, especially the *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *A. terreus*, and *Penicillium* spp. These infections work to Reducing the weight of grains and affecting the color, taste and flavor of the food, in addition to major economic losses [27]. concluded that a number of fungi were isolated that accompanied the rice grains, *A. flavus* *A. niger*, (100%) of, followed by *penicillium* spp, *Trichothecium* spp and *Rhizopus* spp (50, 45, 14)% [28].

Figure 1: Fungal Genera Isolated from Food Products and Cultured on PDA Medium at 25°C for 7 Days

2. The effect of the type of extract on the rates of contamination of foodstuffs with isolated fungi

The results shown in Figure (2) that the alcoholic extract of black pepper was most effective in reducing fungal

contamination rates in food products. The contamination rate was reduced to 27.2% with the alcoholic extract, whereas the rates for the cold and hot water extracts were (38.75, 34.0) %, respectively.

This difference is primarily because the presence of alkaloids in black pepper, particularly Piperine, which significantly lowers fungal contamination rates in food products and Phenolics, flavonoids, alkaloids, amides and steroids, lignans, neolignans, terpenes, chalcones etc and many other compounds that play role antifungal ,antibacterial and insecticidal [29,30].

Figure 2: Effect of Extract Type on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

3. Effect of Extract Concentrations on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

All concentrations significantly affected the reduction of fungal contamination rates, with the 70% concentration being the most effective, resulting in a contamination rate of 5%. The 50% came second with a contamination rate of 12.6%, while the contamination rate increased to 90% in the control treatment Figure (3). The difference in effectiveness between the concentrations is primarily due to the varying levels of the active compounds Piperine and Piperidine. These results align with those reported by [31], who found that a 70% concentration of *Piper* (*Piper longum*) inhibited the growth of *Alternaria* and *Fusarium*.

Figure 3: Effect of Extract Concentrations on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

4. Effect of Fungal Type and Extract Type Interaction on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

The results shown in Table (1) indicate that the sensitivity of fungi varied according to the type of extract. The alcoholic extract was the most effective in reducing contamination rates compared to the cold and hot water extracts. *A. niger* was the most affected compared to other fungi, with contamination rates of (25, 31.25, 22.5) % for the cold water, hot water, and alcoholic extracts, respectively.

The higher ability to inhibit fungi using the alcoholic extract compared to the hot and cold aqueous extracts of black pepper is due to the high concentration of the active substances in the extract and their presence in larger quantities. When using Black Seed Oil, it was also highly effective in controlling fungi and their toxins, especially the fungus *A. flavus* [32].

Table 1: Effect of Fungal Type and Extract Type Interaction on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

Fungal Species	Extract Type	Contaminati on %	Fungal Species	Extract Type	Contaminati on %
<i>A. flavus</i>	Cold	40	<i>Drechslera spp</i>	Cold	32.5
	Hot	36.25		Hot	31.25
	Alcoholic	25		Alcoholic	22.5
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	Cold	35	<i>Rhizoctonia spp</i>	Cold	38.75
	Hot	35		Hot	28.75
	Alcoholic	26.25		Alcoholic	25
<i>A. niger</i>	Cold	25	<i>Alternaria spp</i>	Cold	30
	Hot	31.25		Hot	32.5
	Alcoholic	22.5		Alcoholic	50
<i>A. terreus</i>	Cold	47.5	<i>Curvularia spp</i>	Cold	57.5
	Hot	42.5		Hot	37.5
	Alcoholic	26.25		Alcoholic	22.5
<i>Penicillium spp</i>	Cold	42.5			
	Hot	31.25			

	Alcoholic	25
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5. Effect of Fungal Type and Extract Concentration Interaction on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

Table (2) refer to the concentrations used in the study varied in their effectiveness at reducing fungal contamination rates. The 70% concentration completely inhibited *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, and *Drechslera* 0% . However, contamination rates increased to (6.7, 13.3, 5, 6.7, 8.3) for *A. fumigatus*, *A. terrus*, *Penicillium spp.*, *Rhizoctonia spp*, *Alternaria spp*, and *Curvularia spp* respectively.

On the other hand, Table. Refer to a 50% concentration, contamination rates decreased for all fungi, with *A. niger* being the most sensitive at 11.7% compared to the control, where contamination increased to 90%. The reduced sensitivity of fungi to varying extract concentrations may be due to differences in the concentration of active compounds, such as Piperine and Piperidine. [33] found that increasing the concentration of active compounds in an extract increased fungal sensitivity.

Table 2: Effect of Fungal Type and Extract Concentration Interaction on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

Fungal Species	Concentration %	Contaminati on %	Fungal Species	Concentrati on %	Contaminati on %
<i>A. flavus</i>	0	90	<i>Drechslera spp</i>	0	90
	30	31.7		30	16.7
	50	13.3		50	8.3
	70	0		70	0
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	0	90	<i>Rhizoctonia spp</i>	0	90
	30	20		30	18.3
	50	11.7		50	10
	70	6.7		70	5
<i>A. niger</i>	0	90	<i>Alternaria spp</i>	0	90
	30	11.7		30	36.7
	50	3.3		50	16.7
	70	0		70	6.7
<i>A. terrus</i>	0	90	<i>Curvularia</i>	0	90
	30	31.7		30	38.3
	50	20		50	20
	70	13.3		70	8.3
<i>Penicillium spp</i>	0	90			
	30	23.3			
	50	13.3			
	70	5			

6. Effect of Extract Type and Concentration Interaction on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

Refer the results in Table (3) to evident that the alcoholic extract provided better protection compared to the cold and hot water extracts. At a 70% concentration, the contamination rate was 1.1%, while the contamination rates were 10.6% and 3.3% for cold and hot water extracts, respectively, at the same concentration. For a 50% concentration, the contamination rate was 3.9% for the alcoholic extract. The 30% concentration for all extracts had the least effect on reducing contamination rates.

Table 3: Effect of Extract Type and Concentration Interaction on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

Extract Type	Concentration	Contamination %
Cold	0	90
	30	34.4
	50	20
	70	10.6
Hot	0	90
	30	27.8
	50	15
	70	3.3
Alcoholic	0	90
	30	13.9
	50	3.9
	70	1.1

7. Effect of Extract Type and Concentration, and Fungal Species Interaction on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

Table (4) highlights the effectiveness of treatments in reducing fungal contamination rates in food products. Food products treated with a 70% concentration of the alcoholic extract showed a complete reduction in

contamination rates for all fungi except *Alternaria spp*, which had a contamination rate of 10% at the same concentration compared to the control where contamination increased to 90%. Contamination rates varied with the cold and hot water extracts across all concentrations.

Table 4: Effect of Extract Type, Concentration, and Fungal Species Interaction on Fungal Contamination Rates in Food Products

Fungal Species	Extract Type	Concentration	Contamination %	Fungal Species	Extract Type	Concentration	Contamination %
<i>A. flavus</i>	Cold	0	90	<i>Drechslera spp</i>	Cold	0	90
		30	50			30	25
		50	30			50	15
		70	0			70	0
	Hot	0	90		Hot	0	90
		30	35			30	25
		50	20			50	10
		70	0			70	0
	Alcoholic	0	90		Alcoholic	0	90
		30	10			30	10
		50	0			50	0
		70	0			70	0
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	Cold	0	90	<i>Rhizoctonia spp</i>	Cold	0	90
		30	25			30	30
		50	15			50	25
		70	0			70	0
	Hot	0	90		Hot	0	90
		30	25			30	20
		50	10			50	15
		70	0			70	0
	Alcoholic	0	90		Alcoholic	0	90
		30	5			30	5
		50	0			50	0
		70	0			70	0
<i>A. niger</i>	Cold	0	90	<i>Alternaria spp</i>	Cold	0	90
		30	10			30	50
		50	0			50	30
		70	0			70	10
	Hot	0	90		Hot	0	90
		30	10			30	40
		50	0			50	20
		70	0			70	10
	Alcoholic	0	90		Alcoholic	0	90
		30	0			30	40
		50	0			50	20
		70	0			70	10
<i>A. terreus</i>	Cold	0	90	<i>Curvularia spp</i>	Cold	0	90
		30	40			30	30
		50	15			50	20
	Hot	70	0		Hot	70	0
		0	90			0	90
		30	30			30	30

	Alcoholic	50	10		Alcoholic	50	15
		70	0			70	0
		0	90			0	90
		30	15			30	25
		50	0			50	10
<i>Penicillium spp</i>	Cold	0	90			70	0
		30	40			0	90
		50	15			30	20
	Hot	70	0			50	10
		0	90			70	0
		30	20			0	90
		50	10			30	10
	Alcoholic	70	0			50	0
		0	90			70	0
		30	10			0	90
50		0	30	10			
		70	0				

Conclusion

These results clearly demonstrate the efficacy of the cold, hot water, and alcoholic extracts, with the alcoholic extract providing complete protection for grains, particularly at 70% concentration. Studies have also indicated that basil extract, at concentrations of 20%, 40%, 60%, and 80%, was effective against fungi such as *Alternaria spp*, *Curvularia spp*, *Fusarium spp*, and *Penicillium spp* isolated from corn and pistachios. Higher concentrations (60% and 80%) of the alcoholic extract reduced contamination rates to 2%, whereas the water extract at the same concentration reduced contamination to 15%. *Mentha* extract was also effective against fungi like *A. nidulans*, *Rhizoctonia*, and *Penicillium* at various concentrations, reducing fungal growth [34].

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